

GEOGRAPHY**Impact of Sugar Factory on the Socio-Economic life of Sugarcane Growers – Shri. Siddheshwar Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd. Kumathe Solapur****B.T.Nikam¹****Dr. B.R. Phule²****Sou. V.L. Bansode³****V.B. Bandgar⁴****ABSTRACT:**

Sugarcane is transforming life of Maharashtra's rural folk. From agriculture to political sugar industry playing very active role and its allied institutions supported to rural upliftment. In present study aim to fine the impact of sugarfactory on the socio-economic life of sugarcane growers. For this Shri. Siddheshwar Sahakari Sakhar Karkahana Ltd. Kumathe Solapur is selected to test the impact. For the study researcher prepared and modified pilot tested interview schedule. Interviews from 120 collected from the 10 different villages across Malshiras Tahsil. The questions are asked to identify social and economical change in the sugarcane growers. The raw data is processed through SPSS, version – 10 software system. From the obtained results it is understood that Shri. Siddheshwar Sahakari Sakhar Karkahana Ltd. Kumathe Solapur is responsible for upliftment of sugarcane growers.

Keywords – Co-Operative Sugar Factory, Rural Development, Social and Economical change.

INTRODUCTION:

Sugar industry is most important source of income in agriculture sector. In India sugar industry has an importance of footloose industries in India. Sugar canes transforming life of Maharashtra rural life from agriculture to political sugar industry playing a vital role in rural life platforms. Sugarcane cultivation is the base of sugar factory which provides raw material. Sugar factories are giving inputs in various forms for the development of surrounding rural area. Here attempt has been made to take the review of role of Shri. Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana, Venunagar – Pandharpur in the development of status of sugarcane farmers.

STUDY REGION:

The region under study lies between the North latitudes 17⁰33' to 17⁰ 59' 05" and 75⁰44' to 75⁰58'03" east longitude with an area of 746.30 Sq. Km. The tahsil of north Solapur consists of about 40 rural settlements and the city of Solapur itself. The North Solapur tahsil in the district of Solapur possesses

very significant positions, socially and economically. Despite, this fact the region is expected is backward due to various physical and social reasons.

OBJECTIVES :

- 1) To find the status and historical background of Siddheshwar S.S.K. Ltd. Kumathe-Solapur
- 2) To analyze the social and economical change among sugarcane growers.

DATABASE METHODOLOGY:

The information and data are the most important for research, without proper information and data, research can not be carried out. No desirable conclusion and generalization may be obtained without proper data analysis. Hence, the data that is basic tools of the research is collected from different sources such as published and unpublished works, Reports and census of Government. Publication have used for the analysis purpose. With the help of interviews, the first hand data is collected and result is interpreted accordingly. The present study relies upon primary data. The represented data is interpreted and analyzed to find the desirable result and conclusion.

HISTORICAL REVIEW OF SUGAR FACTORY:

Late. Appasaheb Kadadi opens the sugar factory in late 1969. Appasaheb Kadadi is certainly a great man and others can follow his foot prints. He is a visionary and has fore sight. Appasaheb feels that inspiration from the other's work. He gave the promise for social welfare of farmers in south Solapur tahsil According to that he registered co-operative sugar factory in 02/07/1969. Initially Appasaheb visit farmer and convinced them for share to Siddheshwar Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd. Vennagar. Farmer has ambiguity for investment to Sugar Co-operative. As Solapur district belongs to drought prone area and unfavorable irrigation facilities. The farmer not had capital to invest in the share, though Appasaheb Kadadi is the offer them loan from the 'Bank of India' and mortgage his property. This loan recovered by payment of Sugarcane to the Siddheshwar Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd. Kumathe-Solapur.

Appasaheb Kadadi is a great task master and an efficient administrator. He visited Malshiras tahsil and recognizes marvelous changes from the Sugar Co-operative. He thinks implementation of this model at Kumathe in South Solapur Tahsil. His dreams executed when his Sugar factory start crushing in a year 1971-72. His idea for Sugar co-operative appreciated from all corners of society.

Appasaheb take historical decision to initiate cancer and research Hospital under the gees of Siddheshwar Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana. Appasaheb also promote irrigation facilities to sustain sugarcane crop in the

command area of the Siddheshwar Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana. He starts Dahigaon, Alagi, Sadepur and Vadapur lift irrigation schemes and give promotion to the dug wells and Bore wells. Appasaheb Kadadis vision to see Siddheshwar Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana is family. Right now Siddheshwar Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana has 278 acres of land and 285 villages under the command area. Total shareholders 2424 in 1971 and increasing by 19400 in a year 2009-2010. This Siddheshwar Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana (factory) is now giving economical stability among the farmers and employees.

Table 1: Sample Design for selection of Village and Households

Name of Village	Number of Sample	Small Farmer	Medium Farmer	Big Farmer
Bhagaiwadi	12	04	04	04
Darphal Gavadi	12	04	04	04
Haglur	12	04	04	04
Honsal	12	04	04	04
Kegoan	12	04	04	04
Kumathe	12	04	04	04
Pakhani	12	04	04	04
Shelgi	12	04	04	04
Telgoan	12	04	04	04
Tirhe	12	04	04	04
Total	120	40	40	40

Source: Compiled by researcher.

Sample villages are selected on the basis of key characteristics. These all are maintained in the table 1. The North Solapur tahsil are climatically dry area. In North Solapur tahsil ground water, small reservoirs are source of agricultural irrigation. In the present study 10 villages from North Solapur tahsil are selected are indentified and confirmed to collect a data from sugarcane growers. From the each village twelve samples are selected from the each category four samples are selected. In this research excursion I found that data collection from North Solapur tahsil is difficult due to the language barer majority of the people are native to Kannada language. There are I take help of my friend Prof. Maske, Prof. Dede Sir, who translate me the responses of the sugarcane grower to these questions. The villagers from the North Solapur are Darphal(G), Honsal, Pakhani, Bhagaiwadi , Haglur ,Tirhe, Kegoan Kumathe, Shelgi, Telgoan villages of North Solapur tahsil .

Table 2: Housing Condition of Respondents

Land Size Category	Number of Facilities in the Group	Year	Pacca (%)	Medium (%)	Kaccha (%)
Small Farmer	40	1970-71	00	10.00(30.00)	23.00(70.00)
	40	2010-11	17.50(52.50)	11.66(35.00)	4.16(12.50)
Medium Farmer	40	1970-71	4.51(15.00)	10.83(32.50)	17.50(52.50)
	40	2010-11	20.00(60.00)	5.83(17.50)	7.50(22.50)
Big Farmer	40	1970-71	3.33(10.00)	9.16(27.50)	20.83(62.50)
	40	2010-11	27.50(82.50)	3.33(10.00)	2.50(7.50)
Total	120	1970-71	8.33	30.00	71.66
	120	2010-11	65.00	21.66	14.16

Source : Compiled by researcher.

Table Number 2 indicates that housing condition of Sugarcane grower of Siddheshwar S.S.K. Ltd. Kumthe-Solapur. In the small farmer category the pacca houses are 52.50 percent in the year 2010-11, which is not seen in the year 1970-71. The medium scale houses in this category are 30.00 percent in the 1970-71 which is increased to 35.00 percent in the 2010-2011. The situation of Kaccha house in 1970-71 are 70.00 percent and which is drastically decreased up to 12.50 percent. In the medium sugarcane grower the Pacca houses increased form 15.00 percent 60.00 percent, medium scale houses decreased form 32.50 percent for 17.50 percent and Kaccha decreased from 52.50 percent to 22.50 percent. In big farmers category of pacca houses are increased form 10.00 percent to 82.50 percent. In the medium level houses condition decreased by 27.50 percent to 10.00 percent during the period 1970-71 to 2010-11. It is amazing to see the kaccha house condition among the big farmer is drastically decreased from 62.50 percent to 7.50 percent in the four decades.

The majority contribution to increase the housing condition is because of good price to sugarcane crop. This has been clicked during discussion with sugarcane growers. In short it is found that Pacca house condition is rise from 8.33 percent to 65.00 percent and kaccha house condition decreased from 61.66 percent to 14.16 percent.

Table 3(A): Status of Domestic Materials

Category of Farmers	Number of Farmers	Year	Chair (%)	Table (%)	Fans (%)	Radio (%)	TV (%)
Small Farmer	40	1970-71	00	00	00	10.83	00
	40	2010-11	22.50(67.50)	16.66(50.00)	26.66(80.00)	30.00(90.00)	28.33(85.00)
Medium Farmer	40	1970-71	00	00	00	11.66 (35.00)	00
	40	2010-11	26.66(80.00)	20.00(60.00)	25.83(77.50)	29.16(87.50)	30.83(92.50)
Big Farmer	40	1970-71	07.50(22.50)	4.16(12.50)	6.66(20.00)	9.16(27.50)	5.00(15.00)
	40	2010-11	27.50(82.50)	24.16(72.50)	33.33(100)	33.33(100)	33.33(100)
Total	120	1970-71	7.50	4.16	6.66	31.66	5.00
	120	2010-11	76.66	60.83	85.83	92.50	84.16

Source : Compiled by researcher.

Table No. 3 enumerate economic condition of sugarcane grower. Out of total 120 samples 40 each samples are divided in the three categories i.e. small farmer, medium farmer and big farmer. Through this result it is found the perfect economic transformation among sugarcane grower. In this small farmer category the transformation rate of home appliances are very higher than the tow categories.

Table and Chairs:

In this small farmer the number of Table and chairs are zero in the year 1970-71. Now in the sugarcane growers 67.50% homes have chairs and 50.00% homes have tables. In the medium farmer category chairs and tables are didn't see in the 1970-71 and it is rise up to 80.00 percent and 60.00 percent respectively. In the big farmer category there are 22.50 percent homes and chairs and 2.50 percent homes had table in the year 1970-71. In the year 2010-11 this number is rise up to the 82.50 percent and 72.50 percent respectively. In average the chair and table in the year 1970-71 is rise from the 7.50 and 4.16 percent to 76.66 percent and 60.83 percent respectively. In this region growth in the chair and table are indicated rise their purchasing power. Because these are the important indicators to determine economic upliftment of any class in the society.

Fan, Radio and Television:

In the year 1970-71 the electricity has limited access in the villages. Though fan, television have not demanded in the rural classes. After successive years the electricity spread in the rural pockets and electronic appliances are rising firstly.

In the small farmer and medium farmer category there was fans and television didn't observe in the collected data. In the year 1970-71 there was dramatically rise the number of fan and Television in the small and medium farmer category. The number is increased up to 80.00 percent and 85.00 percent respectively. The television is very popular entertaining appliances in the home. After DTH (Direct Television Home) technology. There was popularity is increased in many fields. In medium farmer category fan and Television is increased up to 77.50 percent and 92.50 percent respectively. In the year 1970-71 in the big farmer home fan and television are seen in the 20.00 percent and 15.00 percent prospectively. This is the prime indicator to judge the economic condition of same big farmer is very high. But many big farmers don't have physical asset. This may be because of seasonal crops and low agricultural productivity. In the big farmer all the homes have fan and television.

The radio is very popular mass media device even before to independence. Therefore it is not surprising to see Radio in the small farmers home. Bit in the social and economical development process the accessibility of this device is increasing. The growth of Radio in the small category is 90.00

percent, in medium farmer category it is 87.50 percent and in the big farmer category all own Radio. In the short it is surprise see that, the growth of the fan is 6.66 percent, 85.83 percent, Television increased by 5.00 percent to 84.60 percent and Radio rise from 31.66 percent to 92.50 percent respectively.

Table 3(B) Status of Domestic Materials

Category of Farmers	Number of Facilities in the Group	Year	Freeze (%)	Washing Machine (%)	Cooler (%)	Phone (%)	Gas (%)
Small Farmer	40	1970-71	00	00	00	00	00
	40	2010-11	14.16 (42.50)	19.16 (57.50)	1.66 (5.00)	6.66 (20.00)	28.33 (85.00)
Medium Farmer	40	1970-71	00	00	00	00	1.66 (5.00)
	40	2010-11	12.50 (37.50)	14.16 (42.50)	5.00 (15.00)	9.16 (27.50)	28.33 (85.00)
Big Farmer	40	1970-71	00	00	00	00	6.66 (15.00)
	40	2010-11	19.16 (57.50)	27.50 (68.06)	10.83 (32.50)	21.66 (65.00)	30.83 (92.50)
Total	120	1970-71	00	2.50	00	00	8.33
	120	2010-11	45.83	60.83	17.50	37.50	87.50

Source : Compiled by Researcher.

Freeze and Cooler:-

The freeze and Cooler in farmers home is dream in 1970-71 period. The technological development and economic growth chiefly responsible for transforming whole society. Here I analyze that the freeze and cooler in the farmers home is common property. In the small farmer category there was no freeze and cooler in the year 1970-71. In a year 2010-11 this number is raised by 42.50 percent and 20.00 percent respectively. In a medium farmer category the freeze and cooler in a year 1970-71 is zero were as in 2010-11 this number increased by 37.50 percent and 27.50 percent respectively. Even in the big farmer category freeze and cooler doesn't observed in the year 1970-71 but the growth percentage in the year 2010-11 is very high i.e. freeze increased up to 57.50 percent and cooler increased up to 65.00 percent. This clearly indicate that the number of freeze and cooler highest among the big farmer. This is because of sugarcane grower in this category has purchase power. This may be because of sugarcane like cash crop. During the focal discussion and field visit. I visited to many sugarcane grower homes and found that especially a big farmer economic change is very high and they affirm that sugarcane make them worthy to transform their family.

Overall the average rise in the freeze and cooler is up to 45.83 percent and 37.50 percent respectively.

Gas and Washing machines:-

The cooking fuel has always been problematic issue among farmer. Though there were several traditional cooking fuels available in the

agriculture. This has been limitation because of many factors. The education level of common is increasing and they know the health hazards of traditional fuels. Therefore they always desire to get a smoke free cooking fuel like LPG. In the study the attempt is find that accessibility of liquid petroleum gas (LPG) among the different strata of sugarcane grower in the study area. The LPG is not seen among the small farmer and medium farmer category in a year 1970-71. Meanwhile in the year 2010-11 the number is increased up to 57.50 percent and 42.50 percent among small farmers and medium farmers group. In the big farmer category 7.50 percent sugarcane grower has gas. This changed in the year 2010-11 the number is increased up to 68.06 percent. This is the highest growth rate seen only in the big farmer category.

The washing machine is not seen month the any farmer in the year 1970-71. In a year 2010-11 the situation is rise among the all farmer category. In small farmer, medium farmer, big farmer category is 5.00 percent, 15.00 and 32.50 percent respectively in the year 2010-11. In average the number is only rise up to 17.50 percent.

Phone / Cell Phone / Mobile:-

After mobile revolution the increase of mobile phone in India. Even though rural pockets are well connected to the mobile network. Therefore it is obvious that in the study area. There are number of phone in all category are raised more than 80.00 percent. In the small farmer and medium farmer category they didn't have any mobile phones. This was rise by 85.00 percent in a year 2010-11. In the big farmer category 15.00 percent farmer had phones in the year 1970-71 where as in 2010-11 the number of phones increased up to 92.50 percent. In an average the phone in the study area is raised from 8.33 percent to 87.50 percent.

Table 3(C):Status of Vehicles own by the sugarcane grower

Category of Farmers	Number of Facilities in the Group	Year	Two wheeler (%)	Four wheeler (%)
Small Farmer	40	1970-71	00	00
	40	2010-11	22.50(67.50)	0.83(2.50)
Medium Farmer	40	1970-71	4.16(12.50)	00
	40	2010-11	20.00(60.00)	15.83(47.50)
Big Farmer	40	1970-71	17.50(52.50)	04.16(12.50)
	40	2010-11	27.50(82.50)	20.83(62.50)
Total	120	1970-71	21.66	04.16
	120	2010-11	70.00	45.83

Source : Compiled by Researcher.

The two wheeler and four wheeler among sugarcane grower is negligible in the year 1970-71. In the small category the two are not observed in a year 1970-71, this number is increased up to 65.70 percent in the year

2010-11. In the medium farmer category 12.50 percent respondent had 2 wheelers and in a year 2010-11 this number is reach up to 60.00 percent. This very impressing to see that 52.50 percent. Big farmer had two wheeler in a year 1970-71. Two wheeler in a year 2010-11 increasing by 52.50 percent. The four wheeler in the small farmer and medium farmer category is didn't observed in a year 1970-71. This number is raised up to 2.50 percent and 47.50 percent respectively. It is delighted to seen that 47.50 percent, medium farmer has four wheelers. This is clearly shows that the medium farmer growth has now able to purchase for wheeler and this is because of rise in the economic level. There are several reasons to upliftment of farmer in the poor to medium and upper class. In the sugarcane play crucial role during rise in the economic level. In the big farmer category 12.50 percent respondent had four wheelers during 1970-71 year. This number increased up to 62.50 percent in a year 2010.11 over all growth of four in the sugarcane grower is from 4.66 percent to 45.83 percent during four decades.

CONCLUSION:

The study of Shri. Siddheshwar Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd. Kumathe-Solapur and its command area highlight the following conclusion –

1. Sugarcane is transforming life of Maharashtra's rural folk. From agriculture to political sugar industry playing very active role and its allied institutions supported to rural upliftment. In present study aim to fine the impact of sugar factory on the socio-economic life of sugarcane.
2. The growth and development of Shri siddheshwar sugar factory since last two decades has helped to do development in its command areas.
3. Shri siddheshwar sugar factory has made comfortable living of the ordinary farmers by providing well equipped standard of high living.
4. Since last 5 – six years it is observed that farmers from the command Areas are very well progressed and developed which is keenly indicating not only economical but social, educational and agricultural Growth in condition.
5. Shri siddheshwar sugar factory not only helped in the growth of financial condition of the command area but also improved the Irrigated command area by creating awareness among the farmers of as section about the exact need of present.
6. In short, the sugar factory and its command areas leading towards high growth and developed in field area.

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